

formed with 3-methyl and 5-methyl substituted binary imine or oxime Ni(II) complexes; one of the positions 3 or 5 being already occupied by the methyl group. This shows that the bromination reaction takes place in Ni(II) complexes over benzene ring at positions 3 and 5. This is due to different orientation effect of phenolic oxygen (-O) and azomethine group (>C=N-).

Amine exchange takes place when brominated copper(II) and nickel(II) imine compounds are treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate. The H of the imine group is replaced by -OH oxime group.

The analysis, magnetic moments and spectral properties of the above bis-brominated imine or oxime complexes and the corresponding bis-complexes obtained by the reaction of metal ammine with brominated ligand are found to be similar.

All complexes are non-electrolyte in chloroform solution and addition of aqueous silver nitrate to an ethanolic solution of the brominated complex does not yield a precipitate. This shows that there is no free bromine in the complex or coordinated bromide ions thereby confirming that bromination of the benzene molecule has occurred.

The brominated nickel(II) imine and oxime complexes are typical product of the bromination reactions. Like [1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneamine]-Ni(II)⁶, these compounds are diamagnetic and show a single absorption in the range 540-560 nm in imine complex and 600-620 nm in oxime complex in their visible spectra. This indicates the square planar geometry of these compounds.

All brominated copper(II) imine and oxime complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu=1.8$ to 1.95 B.M.) indicating the presence of one unpaired electron. There is no change in the paramagnetic value of brominated compounds of copper(II) complexes from those without bromo substitution. The visible absorption spectra of brominated compounds exhibit one broad band at 560 nm in case of imine compounds and at ~ 650 nm in case of oxime compounds¹¹.

The ir spectra of imine derivatives of 2-hydroxyacetophenone Schiff base compounds contain two characteristic strong bands at 1600 and 3300 cm^{-1} which are associated with the >C=N and N-H bond stretches⁹. Similarly, oxime complexes show one band at ~ 1625 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=N stretching¹². Substitution of bromine in the benzene ring at 3 and 5 positions or 3 or 5 position depending upon the substituents present, results in the increase of the C=N and N-H stretching frequencies. The ir spectra of the brominated complexes show these bands at 1610-1625 cm^{-1} in imine complex, 1640 cm^{-1} in oxime complex and 3310-3325 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=N and N-H, stretching, which are increased by 10 to 25 cm^{-1} unit.

The ir spectra of brominated bis-imine Schiff base complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) show a

N-H stretching band at ~ 3320 cm^{-1} . The disappearance of the 3320 cm^{-1} band after N-substitution reaction can be attributed to the replacement of the N-H hydrogen in brominated bis-copper(II) and nickel(II) imine Schiff base complexes by hydroxyl (-OH) groups.

Above results show that there is no effect of N-substituents on ring substitution reactions thereby suggesting that the orientation of the incoming bromine remains the same in imine (N-H) or oxime (N-OH) compounds.

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Nickel(II) Mixed Ligand Complexes with Schiff Bases Containing Nitrogen and Oxygen Donor Atoms†

B. T. THAKER

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

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BIS Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are reported¹⁻⁸ to form coordination complexes with various bivalent metal ions. Similarly, mixed imine and aliphatic diamine Schiff base complexes derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy

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acetophenone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been reported^{4,5} with bipoisitive metal ions.

An attempt was, therefore, made to study the reaction of aromatic diamine with ternary nickel(II) complexes through direct and amine exchange reactions. The structure of the complexes have been discussed on the basis of experimental data.

Experimental

All the six complexes used for the reactions with aromatic diamines were prepared according to literature procedure^{4,5}.

- (i) Reactions with [salicylaldehydato or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato, 2-hydroxy-acetophenonato]Ni(II) and [salicylaldehydato, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydato]Ni(II) :

o-Phenylenediamine (*o*-PhDA) or *p*-phenylene diamine (*p*-PhDA) (0.2 mole) in ethanol was added to a suspension (0.2 mole) of the title mixed ligand complexes in 50 ml ethanol. The well stirred reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The reddish (*o*-PhDA) or blackish (*p*-PhDA) mixed ligand diamine (tetradentate) complexes separated out. It was filtered, washed with ethanol, air dried and recrystallized from chloroform.

- (ii) Reactions with imine mixed Schiff base complexes of nickel(II) :

The reactions were carried out with the following mixed compounds :

- (a) [salicylideneamine, 1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II) ;
- (b) [salicylideneamine, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine]Ni(II) ;
- (c) [2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine, 1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II).

o-Phenylenediamine (*o*-PhDA) or *p*-phenylenediamine (*p*-PhDA) (0.2 mole) solution in ethanol in excess was added to a suspension of the complex (a), (b) or (c) (0.2 mole) in 50 ml ethanol. The

reaction mixture was stirred well and the solid compound obtained as above in each case was filtered, washed with ethanol and air dried.

- (iii) Reaction with *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene[salicylideneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxy phenyl) ethylideneaminato]Ni(II) :

An excess of ethylene diamine was added to the above title compound (1 g). In this reaction ethylenediamine acts as a solvent. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr, stirred well and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and air dried.

Analyses, tlc, molar conductance, magnetic and spectral studies for characterization of these complexes were carried out as detailed earlier^{5,6}. TGA data were obtained from an assembly with a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ upto 600° in air. Relevant data have been presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The homogeneity of all the metal complexes was confirmed by tlc analysis⁷. The molar conductance of all nickel(II) complexes in chloroform shows them to be nonelectrolytes.

On reaction of mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with (*o*-PhDA) or (*p*-PhDA), the diamine (tetradentate) mixed Schiff base complexes form as follows :

Same complexes were also obtained by amine exchange process, i.e. by treating mixed amine Schiff base complexes with *o*-PhDA or *p*-PhDA

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

	Ni	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Electronic spectral band λ_{max} nm
		C	H	N	
a. [Ni(Sal)(OHA) <i>o</i> -PhDA]	15.24 (15.18)	65.19 (65.16)	9.91 (4.13)	9.51 (9.11)	560
b. [Ni(Sal)(OHA) <i>p</i> -PhDA]	14.94 (15.18)	64.92 (65.16)	4.01 (4.13)	9.60 (9.11)	570
c. [Ni(NaPh)(OHA) <i>o</i> -PhDA]	14.00 (13.45)	68.50 (68.69)	3.98 (4.12)	6.63 (6.41)	565
d. [Ni(NaPh)(OHA) <i>p</i> -PhDA]	13.81 (13.45)	68.90 (68.69)	4.15 (4.12)	6.06 (6.41)	575
e. [Ni(NaPh)(Sal) <i>o</i> -PhDA]	14.22 (13.89)	67.92 (68.13)	3.86 (3.78)	6.64 (6.62)	560
f. [Ni(NaPh)(Sal) <i>p</i> -PhDA]	13.60 (13.89)	68.50 (68.13)	3.65 (3.78)	6.97 (6.62)	570

as under :

From the above reaction it can be inferred that a large excess of the less basic aromatic diamine can replace more basic ammonia, but the rate of reaction is very slow with aromatic diamines as an incoming amine.

The amine exchange reaction can occur with good yield when the reacting amine is more basic than the amine initially used to form the imine complex^{8,9}. Thus, ethylene diamine is replaced by 1,2-diamino propane as reported earlier⁴. In addition, such reactions appear to be favoured by the presence of a large excess of exchanging amine.

It has also been observed that the amine exchange reaction between N,N'-o-phenylene[salicylideneamino, 1-(2-hydroxy-phenyl) ethylideneamino]Ni(II) and ethylene diamine did not take place, even though the aliphatic diamine is more basic than the aromatic diamine.

It may be suggested that the coordinated aromatic diamines may to some extent involve back donation from the metal resulting in some double bond character to metal-nitrogen bond and lowering the effective positive charge on the azomethine carbon. Therefore, carbon of azomethine group would not encourage nucleophilic attack. This indicates the higher stability of aromatic diamine Schiff base complexes than that of aliphatic diamine.

The visible absorption spectra of the complexes obtained from both the methods show shoulder between 560 to 575 nm. This shows that the compounds are square planar in structure. Such structure is also supported by diamagnetic nature of all the complexes.

The ir spectra of the 1:1:1 nickel(II) compounds do not exhibit the band in the 3400 cm⁻¹ range indicating that -OH hydrogens of aldehyde or ketone get dissociated after complexation. The band at 1625 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the aldehydic and ketonic C=O. The shift in value is due to the coordination. This band, however, disappears and a new band at 1600 cm⁻¹ appears in the imine Schiff base complexes. This corresponds to C=N stretch and indicates the formation of Schiff base. In the mixed imine nickel(II) Schiff base complexes the band at 3300 cm⁻¹ corresponds to -N-H stretching frequency. The disappearance of the 3300 cm⁻¹ band after amine exchange reaction can be attributed to the replacement of the N-H hydrogen by an aromatic diamine. The two weak bands observed at 2920 and 2860 cm⁻¹ correspond to C-H stretching frequency due to -CH₃ group and aldehydic C-H, respectively.

The percentage loss in weights on heating, at various temperatures indicate the gradual decomposition of the complexes. The abrupt change in weight shows the decomposition of the ligand. The order of thermal stability is [Ni(Sal)(OHA)-o-PhDA] (220°) ~ [Ni(NaPh)(OHA)-o-PhDA] (220°) ~ [Ni(Sal)(NaPh)-o-PhDA] (220°) > [Ni(Sal)(OHA)-p-PhDA] (200°) ~ [Ni(NaPh)(OHA)-p-PhDA] (200°) > [Ni(Sal)(NaPh)-p-PhDA] (180°).

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Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Iron(II) Complexes of 3-Carboxy-4-Hydroxy Azobenzene as Indicators in Acid Base Titrations

S. D. GOSWAMI*, B. M. PATEL and BIPIN PATEL

Department of Chemistry, P. G. Science College, Bardoli-394 601

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THE use of metal complexes as visual indicators in acid base titrations has been investigated in recent years¹⁻⁴. Zinc(II), cadmium(II) and manganese(II) complexes of 1-[2-pyridylazo]-2-phenanthrol (PAP) have been used as indicators in the titration of strong base against strong acid⁵. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the use of metal complexes of 3-carboxy-4-hydroxy azobenzene (CHAB) as indicators in acid base titrations.

Experimental

3-Carboxy-4-hydroxy azobenzene: Aniline was diazotised and immediately coupled with salicylic acid in alkaline medium. The solution was then acidified with dilute acetic acid and the yellowish